

Kinetics of Oxidation of Benzaldehydes by Permanganate in Sulphuric Acid-Acetic Acid Mixture

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The oxidation of substituted benzaldehydes by acid permanganate has been studied in acetic acid-sulphuric acid mixture. The reaction is first order each in the substrate and oxidant. The rate of reaction increases with the increase in sulphuric acid concentration and that the order with respect of H^+ was unity. The solvent effect has been studied at 30° by various acetic acid contents of the medium at constant sulphuric acid concentration. A linear plot of $\log k$ against $(D-1)/(2D+1)$ showed that the reaction is of dipole-dipole nature. The substituent effect showed that electron releasing groups enhance the rate of oxidation while electron withdrawing groups retard the rate.

THE kinetics of oxidation of benzaldehydes by permanganate has been studied by different workers¹⁻³. In our earlier communication⁴, we have reported oxidation in aqueous sulphuric acid. In the present paper, the kinetics of oxidation of benzaldehydes by acid permanganate has been reported with a view to find the nature of reactive species in sulphuric acid-acetic acid mixture and to propose a suitable mechanism.

Results and Discussion

The products from the oxidation of benzaldehyde by permanganate was found to be benzoic acid which was identified as follows. The reaction mixture with little excess of stoichiometric concentration of permanganate at one molar sulphuric acid concentration and 25° was kept till the reaction was completed. The reaction mixture was then extracted with ether, and the extract consisted of the product and acetic acid which was removed by keeping the ether extract in vacuum desiccator containing potassium hydroxide. After removing acetic acid and ether, the solid product so obtained was treated with sodium bicarbonate and filtered. On acidification of the filtrate a white precipitate was formed which on recrystallisation gave a compound with melting point of 120° , which agreed with literature value for benzoic acid. The stoichiometry of the reaction was studied using excess permanganate. The reaction mixture contained $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ permanganate and $8.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ aldehyde in $1M$ sulphuric acid at 25° . It was found that the stoichiometry of the reaction in the ratio of five moles of aldehyde to two moles of permanganate. The following stoichiometry equation can be proposed in acid medium

The reaction was found to be first order in aldehyde and in permanganate respectively. The overall second order rate constant k_2 was calculated using the equation⁵. When acrylamide was added to the reaction mixture no polymerization was observed indicating the absence any free radicals. The rate constants were determined in $1M H_2SO_4$ and 50% HOAC (v/v) in the temperature range 20 to 45° and rate constants and thermodynamic parameters are given in Table 1. The error in

TABLE 1—RATE CONSTANTS AT VARIOUS TEMPERATURES FOR THE OXIDATION OF SUBSTITUTED BENZALDEHYDES BY PERMANGANATE AND KINETIC PARAMETERS

$[RCHO]_0 = [MnO_4^-]_0 = 4.0 \times 10^{-4} M$; $[H_2SO_4] = 1M$;
 $[CH_3COOH] = 50\%$ (v/v); $T = 45^\circ C$

Substituent	Temperature ($^\circ C$)			ΔH^\ddagger k cal/mole	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ e.u.
	20	25	45		
2 : 6 Cl ₂	11.82	16.90	57.90	10.9	16.12
o-NO ₂	2.96	4.44	28.82	13.4	9.65
o Cl	2.53	3.81	17.22	13.5	5.21
2 : 4 Cl ₂	2.11	2.96	11.61	11.0	18.85
-H	1.69	2.35	7.92	10.7	20.55
p-NO ₂	1.48	2.05	6.81	10.6	21.37
2 : 4(NO ₂) ₂	1.06	1.58	5.39	11.4	19.43
p-Cl	0.91	1.21	3.46	9.2	26.79

activation energies is of the order of ≈ 0.5 k cal/mole for all substituents. The free energy of activation is 16.5 ± 0.5 k cal/mole for all substituents.

The solvent effect was studied at constant sulphuric acid concentration but at different compositions of acetic acid-water mixture. The rate increased with increase in percentage of acetic acid. A plot of $\log k$ against $(D-1)/(2D+1)$ was linear indicating the reaction to be dipole-dipole. The rate constants are given in different compositions of acetic acid in Table 2. This was further confirmed

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